

Robotics from the Depths of Earth to Farthest Reaches of the Galaxies and the Importance of Contingencies

Ronnie Bruce^a

^a NASA, Washington, USA

Keywords:

1. Introduction

Robots are used in applications that extend into the depths of the Earth to the vast expanse of our solar system and beyond because of the technology we have at the tip of our fingertips.

2. Aim

The process of building in contingency plans while being able to creatively adapt in the cases where the mission changes direction midstream can be difficult. This requires “thinking outside the box” to be ready for those abrupt changes.

3. Material and methods

Experiencing the evolution of projects such as the Lunar Truck that began as a vehicle that needed to be adaptable to the newest design of spacesuits into the Lunar Electric Rover necessary to sustain two astronauts for up to 14 days with sleeping and sanitary facilities has been challenging yet fulfilling. As the direction of the mission changed from a vision of going to the moon and then mars to visiting Near Earth Objects (NEOs), the 6 wheel modules were replaced with thrusters capable of sending astronauts to visit incoming asteroids. The Robonaut II is another example of design flexibility as a chassis was adapted to create an “off road” version called Centaur II aka R2C2. R2, for short (humanoid robot), was also upgraded by the addition of two climbing manipulators (“legs”) and are currently being fitted for the most advanced biped. Advancements in alternative methods of manufacturing has allowed for the evolution of the project to achieve cost-effective solutions within a reasonable budget.

4. Results

This will instill in people to develop new and fresh technologies for the advancement of mankind while always thinking of a contingency plan for adaptability. As technology is growing at a rapid pace, the implementation of the technology may be already outdated.

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5. Conclusions

I hope to challenge people's perspective and designs to "think outside of the box" and always have a contingency plan as well as a work ethic to implement the vision in a timely manner that can witness the reality of the most advanced humanoid in the solar system to be used aboard the International Space Station.

6. Keywords

NASA Robotics, Robonaut I, Robonaut II, Centaur, Lunar Electric Rover, Space Exploration Vehicle (SEV), Near-Earth Objects (NEOs), Humanoid, hazardous reconnaissance & duty robots, IRAD Telescope, Stellarium Software, 3D Printing, Stereo Lithography, & Biped Robots.

Author biography

Ronnie Bruce I worked for the NASA aerospace community for almost 20 years and contributed to the successful delivery of many projects within the NASA Robotics & Automation Division including the Multi-Mission Space Exploration Vehicle, Lunar Electric Rover, Scout, Modular Robotic Vehicle, Spidernaut, Robonaut 2, Centaur I, Centaur II, ARGOS (Active Response Gravity Offload System), AER-Cam, Exo-Skeleton, Low Impact Docking System, DARPA Robotic Challenge as well as various projects within the NASA Robotics Division. I have also manufactured hardware for the International Space Station, Hubble Telescope, NASA shuttle missions. Now I am working for Schlumberger in the new product development of down hole tools and offshore hardware used in the exploration and completions of Oil Field Production.